

Towards Sustainable Manufacturing: Digital Twins for Enhanced Energy Efficiency

Author: Atieh Khodadadi

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Sanja Lazarova-Molnar

Introduction

The manufacturing industry is responsible for more than 30% of total primary energy consumption and 36% of total greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Rapid industrialization and increasing energy demand necessitate **energy efficiency (EE)** in various industries. Intelligent manufacturing techniques, including **digital twins (DTs)**, offer solutions to **optimize energy consumption, minimize waste, and transition to renewable energy sources**, ensuring comprehensive EE in industrial settings [2].

Overview of a Digital Twin in a manufacturing system.

Goal and Methodology

Goal: Digital Twins for Enhanced Energy Efficiency in Manufacturing Systems.

Challenges

- **Limited data availability:** Obtaining real-time energy consumption data and pertinent parameters from manufacturing systems.
- **Complex system dynamics:** Intricate energy usage patterns and interdependencies within the systems.
- **Integration of hybrid models:** Careful design, validation, calibration, and optimization strategies to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and effectiveness of the hybrid models, typical for this use case.
- **Integration with legacy systems:** Diverse technologies and protocols involved.
- **Integration of renewable energy sources:** Technical incompatibilities, infrastructure limitations, grid stability concerns, retrofitting complexities, and optimizing intermittent renewable sources.
- **Selecting appropriate KPIs and standards:** Identifying necessary standards, KPIs, and data sources to align with the DT goals.
- **High computational requirements:** Requirement of substantial computational resources.
- **Privacy and Security:** Need for strong measures to protect against cyber threats and ensure data integrity and confidentiality.
- **Uncertain energy models:** Complexities stemming from energy consumption patterns, production conditions, and equipment performance uncertainties.
- **Cost considerations:** Need substantial technology, resources, and training investments.
- **Organizational readiness:** Requires the organization to obtain the necessary resources, infrastructure, corporate culture, workforce skills, and process optimization.

References

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